

Jyotiba Phule: Architect of Societal Revolution in 19th-Century India

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Abstract:

Jyotiba Phule (1827-1890) instigated a profound societal revolution in nineteenth-century India, specifically in Maharashtra, by his altruistic actions and philosophical beliefs. Jyotiba Phule (1827-1890) spearheaded social reform in nineteenth-century India, namely in Maharashtra, by advocating for human rights. The nineteenth century was characterised by societal critique and revolution, with a particular focus on nationalism, caste, and gender. Reformers directed their attention towards several concerns related to women, such as the practice of killing female infants, early marriage of girls, limitations on women's access to education, the tradition of Sati (widow self-immolation), the act of shaving widows' heads, and the prohibition on widows remarrying, among other difficulties. Concurrently, he advocated for change directed their attention towards modifying the structures of family and marriage, placing particular importance on the rights and social standing of women. Jyotiba tackled the concerns of gender and caste. He rebelled against the unjust caste system and human rights abuses that had subjugated countless individuals for a thousand years. His defiance of the caste system was accompanied by social and religious changes rooted in principles of equality and kindness. He rose to prominence as the foremost figure representing the marginalised social groups in Maharashtra and was widely recognised as the leader of India's marginalised classes across the nation. He found inspiration in the ideas presented in Thomas Paine's Rights of Man, a work by the American philosopher. This article focuses on Jyotiba as one of the pioneers who gained much prominence as a social reformer in India.

Keywords: social reformer, philosophical beliefs, caste, gender, nationalism, equality, marginalised classes, etc

Jyotiba Phule's Life

Under Jyotibha Phule's father's reign, the authority and grandeur of the Peshwas had considerably declined. During the last days of the Peshwas, the rulers abandoned the practice of fair and just governance. The Brahmins were the favoured caste. Merit was disregarded when they were promoted. The Brahmins were subjected to lenient sanctions for several infractions, which were less severe than the ones mandated by the law. They might potentially reduce their property tax by 50% or even more. Under the rule of Bajirao II, the Brahmins were generously bestowed with philanthropic acts and extravagant banquets.

Conversely, the farmers experienced extreme unhappiness as a result of their reliance on moneylenders, with the bulk of these individuals belonging to the Brahmin caste.

During the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, Brahmins held a position of dominance in society as they were the exclusive class allowed to access education. Conversely, individuals belonging to other castes were deprived of educational opportunities and equal rights in society. Untouchability posed a significant danger to the Shudras and Atishudras, excluding them from the dominant social group. The most widespread issue was social bias and the exploitation of lower castes and women.

Dhananjay Keer asserts that under the Peshwa rule in 19th-century Maharashtra, the Brahmins began to perceive themselves as the dominant social class, enjoying certain privileges and exemptions that were absent in Shivaji's administration. During the reign of the previous Peshwa, the lands owned by Brahmins were evaluated at a rate that was 50% or lower compared to the lands owned by other social classes. Law's severest punishments did not apply to Brahmin wrongdoers. Exclusive rights, monopolies, and philanthropic donations were specifically designated for and bestowed upon Brahmins. During periods of famine, the government of Bajirao II assisted exclusively the Brahmins.

Jyotibha Phule's lineage may be traced down to One Shetiba, his distant ancestor. Khanavali served as the hereditary village of his ancestors in the Purandar subdivision of the Pune district. Shetibe had three sons named Panoji, Govinda, and Krishna. Originally known as the Gorhe family, they changed their names to Jyotibha Phule after establishing a flower shop. During the last years of the Peshwa rule, Jyotibha Phule's ancestors provided the Peshwas with various flower-related products, such as floral mattresses, pillows, and apparel. The letter bestowed upon them a garden and a parcel of property measuring 35 acres as a gift. Jotirao's forebears were employed as greengrocers in the past.

Jyotirao Govindrao Phule, born on April 11, 1827, in Maharashtra, belonged to the Mali caste. His family adopted the surname 'Phule' due to their involvement in the flower trade. Despite societal norms, Phule pursued an education, inspired by Christian missionaries. He completed English studies in 1847 and, at 13, married Savitribai. Witnessing caste-based discrimination, he pledged to uplift lower castes through education. Influenced by Thomas Paine, he critiqued Brahmin hegemony, societal issues, and Hinduism. Phule aimed for a society based on freedom and equality, rejecting Hinduism as a universal religion.

The author's literary style in each of his works exhibited a robust and bold quality. His literary works were a response to the social and ecclesiastical structure of Maharashtra. According to him, the upper castes exerted control over the social hierarchy and received exclusive privileges. Differences existed depending on one's social class and gender. Within the societal framework, the downtrodden were devoid of any semblance of human rights, experiencing solely adversity, substandard treatment, injustice, and exploitation. The religions Puran and Vedas provide endorsement for this particular social structure.

Thus, Phule exhibited a resolute resistance to this. His objective was to develop a novel societal culture that is founded upon principles of equality, fairness, and humanity.

The concept of human rights

Human rights are essential entitlements for all individuals, regardless of gender, ensuring a life marked by respect and worthiness. These fundamental freedoms encompass various aspects such as the right to life, adequate food, suitable shelter, clean air, and political participation. Universal and inherent, human rights are absolute, cannot be taken away, and are intrinsic to human dignity. They contribute to individual growth and protect against persecution and injustice. Pioneers like Raja Ram Mohan Roy, Ishwar Chandra Vidya Sagar, Mahatma Phule, and Sri Narayan Guru advocated for human rights in India during the 18th and 19th centuries, laying the groundwork for the United Nations' 20th-century focus on these rights. Though not explicitly termed "human rights," their principles rooted in human nature are now universally recognized as such.

A Pioneer Human rights crusader in the modern Indian renaissance

Phule provided compelling arguments for the complete eradication of the caste system, including untouchability. He initiated a rebellion against the oppressive caste system that had subjected millions of individuals to persecution for generations. During that time, the Dalit community lacked political, social, educational, and economic rights. He criticised the dual morality of the Brahman system. He asserted the need to ensure that all individuals are afforded equal opportunities. He asserted that every individual is inherently endowed with freedom and equality from birth. Every individual has innate rights. He was a fervent advocate for the protection of human rights for marginalised individuals. His dedication to his wife, Savitribai Phule, motivated him to actively participate in his fight. Savitribai played

a proactive role in the hardships of Mahatma Phule's cause. Following Jyotiba's demise, she took up the role of leading the movement.

Jyotirao Phule's movement unfolded within the colonial context of broader Indian endeavours to address social and political issues. In Maharashtra, both Brahman and non-Brahman groups were engaged in simultaneous and mutually influencing activities, responding to the pressures from British authorities. Phule founded the Satyashodhak Samaj in 1873, coinciding with the influential Prarthana Samaj in Bombay and Arya Samaj in North India. The non-Brahman movement, gaining momentum in the 20th century, mirrored the timeline of elite political organizations.

The Satyashodhak Samaj's establishment closely followed Maharashtra's first political organization, Poona Sarvajanik Sabha, and preceded the Indian National Congress by about twelve years. The Satyashodhak journal, *Din Bandhu*, started in 1875, and predated Brahman nationalist periodicals *Kesari* and *Mahratta* by eight years, showcasing a reciprocal process of influence. This exchange began with the "Indian Renaissance," where early Indian philosophers grappled with Western influence, aiming to transform society through self-evaluation, integration of scientific principles, and reimagining India. Jyotirao Phule's thoughts symbolized the initial expression of this first-generation renaissance thinking during the colonial era.

Women and Shudras are oblivious to the deprivation of their human rights as a result of a Brahmin conspiracy. In addition, Phule highlighted male domination in religious texts. However, despite his belief in *Nirmik*, he does not advocate for intricate rituals and unquestioning devotion to idols and temples. He vehemently objected to futile ceremonies and any intermediary between divinity and humanity. He refuses to acknowledge any offerings to God. He advocates for gender equality, rejects hierarchical dominance, and encourages candour and conscientiousness. Education is crucial for the progress of humanity. In the absence of education, lower castes would perpetually experience oppression and face disadvantages. The deprivation of education is responsible for the deterioration of civilization.

Phule's purpose extended beyond the promotion of literacy. They aimed to produce erudite individuals and advocate for societal change through education. Mahatma Phule expressed his views on various topics such as women's education, education for the lower castes, vocational education, curriculum reform, agricultural education, technical education,

and teacher training. Regrettably, his educational goals faced rejection in India. Mahatma and Savitribai Phule always regarded education as the most effective method to improve the lives of those who were socially disadvantaged. Education has a crucial role in cultivating social awareness and driving social change.

Women and Shudras are oblivious to the systematic denial of their human rights orchestrated by the Brahmin community. Furthermore, Phule underscored the male supremacy prevalent in religious works. However, despite his belief in Nirmik, he does not advocate for intricate rituals and unquestioning devotion to deities' depictions and places of worship. He vehemently objected to futile ceremonies and any intermediary between God and humanity. He refuses to accept any offerings to God. He advocates for gender equality, rejects hierarchical dominance, and encourages candour and conscientiousness. Following death, sin is absent, an absence of an alternate realm, and an absence of the cycle of rebirth. Human beings were obligated to utilise their cognitive ability to navigate through life.

Mahatma Phule's 'Sarvajanik Satya Dharma' served as a declaration of the core tenets of the democratic struggle in this nation, conveying his beliefs and concerns. Amidst a highly traditional setting, the task of establishing a community grounded in the lofty principles of truth, equality, and humanity proved to be arduous. Given such a situation, it was a highly formidable aspiration to dedicate one's life to educating underprivileged groups in the face of dominant classes and their ideology. Nevertheless, they both exerted persistent effort to achieve this objective and paved the way for future endeavours.

In his work, *Sarvajanik Satya-Dharma Pustaka*, Mahatma Phule asserted that all religious texts are written by men and do not encompass the entirety of truth. Some persistent individuals modified these works to adapt them to specific occasions and contemporary needs. Consequently, religions do not provide equal benefits to all individuals and instead foster the emergence of sects and divisions fueled by hatred. The author asserts that humanity is the central theme of existence, beyond considerations of religion, gender, or caste. Furthermore, the author believes in the equality of all individuals throughout society.

Phule's theories are rooted in humanism, and he offered compelling rationales for the complete abolition of the caste system. He revolted against the inequitable caste system that had governed millions of individuals for millennia and subjected them to mistreatment. During that time, the Dalit community lacked political, social, educational, and economic privileges. He criticised the dual morality of the Brahman system. He expressed the belief

that every individual should be afforded equal opportunities. He asserted that every individual is inherently endowed with freedom and equality from birth. Every individual has innate rights. He was a fervent advocate for the protection of human rights for those who were marginalised and mistreated. Sirswal's principles on human rights can be summarised as follows: "All individuals, regardless of their geographical origin, should come together as a unified global family, embracing honesty and without any bias or discrimination based on their local community, region, nation, continent, or religious convictions." Man was given liberty and the ability to enjoy equal rights with others by the Creator. All individuals have been bestowed by the Creator with the privilege to openly articulate their thoughts and viewpoints, as long as they do not inflict any harm onto others. This is considered to be exemplary conduct.

Jyotirao Phule's views on human rights and religion were grounded in a belief in fundamental rights bestowed by a divine being. He advocated for ethical behaviour, emphasizing religious and political freedom for all individuals. Phule rejected idol worship, rituals, extreme self-discipline, predestined fate, and the concept of rebirth. He criticized Hinduism, exposing historical exploitation by Brahmins, and proposed Sarvajanic Satya Dharma as an alternative.

Phule's assault on Hinduism targeted the caste and Varna systems, asserting they were manipulated by Brahmins for exploitation. Despite rejecting Hinduism, he retained a belief in Dharma and worked towards a system based on egalitarianism. Influenced by Thomas Paine, Phule's religion focused on material world matters, promoting an ideal family where members could freely practice their chosen religions. He believed in the coexistence of various religious teachings, emphasizing that no single religion holds exclusive access to truth. Phule advocated against supporting savage Hindu practices and challenged the government's financial backing of temples, rejecting both communalism and unwarranted neutrality towards religious matters.

Women's Emancipation and Empowerment

India has a rich historical legacy, and women have consistently constituted fifty per cent of the population throughout its existence. Nevertheless, their position in society has not been consistent throughout thousands of years. Their position has been assessed through numerous means, and contrasting viewpoints have been expressed regarding their role in different stages of Indian culture. The position of a woman in her family and community has

been influenced by various factors such as foreign invasions, social movements, geographic regions, economic occupations, political stability and instability, and the religious affiliation of her family.

The societal role allocated to women is a reliable indicator of the level of progress it has achieved. The treatment of women by the individuals of a civilization can serve as a criterion for assessing its moral integrity. The status of women is a topic of sociological inquiry and discourse as it mirrors the circumstances of roughly half of a society's populace. An examination of the historical development of human society demonstrates that women did not possess full parity with men in any of the world's societies.

During the 19th century, societal injustice, bias, and exploitation were pervasive, affecting various groups differently. Women, in particular, faced a profoundly inferior social status marked by issues such as early marriage, widowhood, limited education and employment opportunities, and societal afflictions. Widows, marginalized within society, endured precarious situations with restrictions on remarriage. Mahatma Jyotirao Phule and Savitribai Phule, recognizing these challenges, initiated an education movement and established schools to address issues like child marriage and the subordinate position of women. Their literary works and the establishment of the Satya Shodhak Samaj reflected their commitment to advancing the well-being of marginalized groups, especially Shudras, Ati-Shudras, and women. Due to the diligent efforts of socio-political reformers during British rule, substantial advancements were achieved in reducing gender inequities in education, employment, social rights, and other areas. The practices of child marriage, the Sati system, the Devadasi system, the Purdah system, and the prohibition on widow remarriage were either limited or abolished by appropriate legislation. These laws were enacted as a result of the persistent endeavours of socio-political reformers such as Mahatma Jyotirao Phule.

In Phule's day, women lacked social status and were submissive, even within their own houses. They were deprived of all rights within their families and communities. Similarly, they were deprived of an education. The teacher's conduct was a flagrant act of sacrilege and a grievous assault on the principles of Hinduism. Upon establishing his initial educational institution in Pune, Phule, a fervent advocate for social change, encountered vehement opposition from the community when it came to educating Shudra and untouchable females. Jyotirao was considered a foe of Hinduism and a disgrace to the purportedly holy

city by the traditional and uneducated Brahmins of Pune. During a period characterised by strict adherence to traditional beliefs and the social hierarchy, no teacher offered to provide education to females from the lowest social classes. Shortly after Phule's wife, Savitribai embraced the task of teaching, Pune experienced an outburst of unbridled enthusiasm and anger directed against the couple.

Jyotirao and Savitribai advocated for gender equality and opposed the caste system, despite facing severe mistreatment from the Manuwadi and Brahminic factions. Supported by his wife, Savitribai, Jyotiba persevered in his dedication to women's education, undeterred by substantial criticism and challenges. During the meeting on September 15, 1853, Dyananodya expressed his unwavering position about the education of women. He asserts that the enhancement a child undergoes due to their mother is substantial and beneficial. Individuals who prioritise the satisfaction and welfare of this country must diligently focus on the difficult situation faced by women and exert all possible endeavours to provide them with education, if they desire the nation to progress. Taking this into consideration, I established the girls' school at first. My father compelled us to vacate the premises due to the disapproval of my caste relations towards my choice to educate ladies. No individuals were willing to provide room for the school, and we did not have the necessary funds to construct it. Individuals harboured concerns regarding the enrollment of their children in educational institutions, however, Raut Mang and Ranba Mahar Lahuji Ragh successfully convinced members of their caste community about the advantages of acquiring knowledge.

Mahatma Jyotiba Phule and Savitribai were remarkable individuals throughout their respective eras. He facilitated the advancement of women's education by instructing and equipping his wife for formal schooling. Savitribai was the inaugural female schoolteacher in India. In 1848, he established the inaugural educational institution exclusively catering to female students in Pune. He advocated for the education of female students and adults from marginalised areas, namely those belonging to the Shudras and Ati Shudras castes. He established educational institutions. Savitribai established institutions such as the Pune Female Native Schools and the Society for Promoting Education for Mahar, Mangs. Her dedication to female education started in 1847 when she and Sagunabai established a school in Maharwada. On January 1st, 1848, the first educational institution exclusively for women was founded in Bhide's Wada in Pune. Savitribai was appointed as its inaugural headmistress.

She was appointed as a teacher at a time when educating girls was considered disgraceful and offensive to traditional values.

Jyotiba established an adult education institution at Usman Shaikh's Wada. In 1849, Phule founded an additional 18 educational institutions specifically catering to women, Shudras, and Ati-Shudras. Savitribai Phule was awarded the Ideal Teacher Award in 1852 by the School Inspection Committee for her dedication to promoting girls' education. Jyotirao Savitribai's endeavours yielded significant advancements. Government schools were available exclusively for pupils belonging to higher castes. On May 29, 1852, an individual expressed in the Poona Observer that the number of female students at Jyotirao's educational institution was tenfold greater than the number of male students in government institutions.

Recently, there has been accessible information about the establishment of the 'Home for the Prevention of Infanticide' by Savitribai-Jyotirao in 1863. The commendable endeavour undertaken by Savitribai to construct this institution specifically for widows belonging to the Brahman caste is noteworthy. Jyotirao Phule filed a letter to the Under Secretary of the Government of Mumbai on 4 December 1884, documenting this information.

Jyotiba believed in the principle of gender equality. He underscored the importance of women's education and autonomy. He facilitated the inclusion of women in the public sphere. He emphasised that the nation's development hinges on the indispensability of equality and unity. He advocated against underage marriage to promote gender equality.

He established a refuge for women whose husbands had passed away and facilitated the practice of widows remarrying. During that period, widow remarriage was prohibited, whereas child marriage was prevalent among Brahmins and Hindus. A significant number of widows were young, and not all of them adhered to the societal expectations imposed by the orthodox population. Several widows resorted to abortions or deserted their illegitimate children by abandoning them on the streets. In 1863, he constructed a residence for infants to prevent instances of infanticide and suicide. This initiative was prompted by his awareness of the dangers faced by widows who gave birth to children conceived under challenging circumstances after the death of their husbands. In 1854, Phule fervently advocated for the practice of widow remarriage and went so far as to commission the construction of a dwelling specifically for widows belonging to the upper caste. He persistently encouraged individuals to enrol their children in the educational institutions he founded specifically for underprivileged individuals and women.

Emancipation and Welfare of Backward Castes

The establishment of the caste system by Brahmins has not only exerted dominance over Indian society but has also hindered the social mobility and advancement of lower castes, including the Shudras and untouchables. During the British colonial period, there were limited efforts made by social reformers and the government to provide education and empower marginalised socioeconomic sections. The British attempts were shaped by the social reform movements led by various socio-political philosophers such as Mahatma Jyotirao Phule, Shahu Maharaja of Kolhapur, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar, and others. Discrimination against Shudras and scheduled castes continues to exist in rural areas, particularly in private domains such as dining places, schools, temples, and water supplies. It has nearly disappeared from urban areas and the general public domain. Certain Shudras have successfully integrated into urban Indian society, where the influence and importance of caste are less evident and less significant. Despite evidence suggesting a decrease in exclusion, scheduled castes in rural India continue to be often marginalised from participating in local religious activities, highlighting the enduring visibility of caste divisions.

Jyotirao Phule strongly advocated for the eradication of untouchability and the complete caste system, rebelling against the unjust practices that had oppressed many for centuries. He criticized the dual morality of the Brahman system and emphasized the need for equal opportunities, declaring that every individual is inherently free with equal rights from birth. Phule, a staunch advocate for human rights, established the Satya Shodhak Samaj in 1873 to uplift marginalized castes in 19th-century Maharashtra.

In ancient times, Hindu scriptures excluded Shudras and Ati-Shudras from education and equal social standing, perpetuating discriminatory practices. The Satya Shodhak Samaj, founded by Phule in Pune, emerged as a significant non-Brahmin organization, uniting socially disadvantaged groups and workers. The Samaj aimed to empower the oppressed, raise awareness, and oppose the manipulative clergy of the time.

Phule asserted the Samaj's main goal was to emancipate lower classes from Brahmin control by actively opposing untouchability and the caste system. The Samaj refused priestly services and advocated for weddings and ceremonies without priests, leading to legal challenges from Brahmins who were unsettled by these revolutionary ideas.

Jyotiba Phule revolted against the Hindu caste system and the disparities based on the Varna-Vyavastha that were established by human beings. He displayed great bravery in his efforts to enact reforms within Hindu society. He sought to eliminate feelings of inferiority from people's minds. He raised the awareness of the Shudras. He advised them to pursue study and attain positions of power; they are not enslaved, but rather individuals. According to T.L. Joshi, Jyotiba Phule was an early pioneer in challenging India's conventional social structure. From where did he derive the impetus for this uprising, considering that the long-standing societal norms had exerted a firm control over the Indian psyche for thousands of years? Jyotiba was a Satyashodhak, which means he was someone who sought the moral truth of human life. This enduring truth was exemplified by his conviction in the innate liberty of mankind within the cosmos, as supported by modern Western civilization.

He advocated for a humanistic ideology based on the ideas of freedom, egalitarianism, and global fraternity. He challenged the caste system in his writings "Gulamgiri and Brahmanache Kasab". He established the Satyashodhak Samaj group and initiated the process of widespread progress.

Jyotiba Phule asserted that the upper castes exerted control over the social hierarchy and received privileged advantages. Differences existed depending on one's social class and gender. Within the societal framework, the oppressed were devoid of any entitlement to human rights, experiencing solely adversity, substandard treatment, inequity, and exploitation. The religion, Puran and Vedas provide endorsement for this particular social structure. Thus, Phule exhibited a robust resistance to such a social framework. He strived to develop a novel societal model grounded in principles of fairness, compassion, and egalitarianism. He aspired to construct a novel social framework in India based on the ideals of equality, justice, liberty, and brotherhood. He was the pioneer in Indian history who advocated for women's education through the establishment of schools for girls and orphanages for bereaved mothers and their children. He was the inaugural Indian to receive recognition from the British government for his valiant efforts.

The Brahmin Samaj vehemently denounced and physically attacked him for his commendable actions. Nevertheless, he sustained his movement. He devoted his life to the liberation of untouchables, peasants, and women.

Jyotiba Phule established the Native Female School in Pune and also launched the Society for Promoting the Education of Mahars and Mangs. A network of schools was

established in the Pune region via the establishment of these two institutions. Phule commenced the production of two journals, namely Dnyanodaya and Bombay Guardian, to further their endeavours to advocate for female education and the liberation of marginalised communities.

In India, Mahatma Jyotiba Phule emancipated women and Shudras from religious hegemony and laid the foundation for the Backward Class Movement. Mahatma Phule is recognised as the foremost figure in the social reform movement in India. In India, he is acknowledged as the progenitor of the societal upheaval.

Jyotirao exemplified humanity's devotion to their country. He possessed the qualities of a universal individual, like all truly exceptional individuals. He championed the cause of human rights, equity, tranquillity, and prosperity, prioritising them over the pursuit of power. He sought a religion that recognised and promoted social egalitarianism. According to his perspective, religion is a phenomenon that necessitates personal experience rather than just verbal expression. Jyotirao Phule had greater adherence to principles of morality, societal concerns, and logical reasoning than to religious beliefs. During that time, his forceful and rational attack on the belief in reincarnation was quite remarkable. He aimed to correct the Hindus' misconceptions that God would intervene to help them during difficult times and that their destiny was predestined. He instilled in them a sense of autonomy and urged them to champion and safeguard their fundamental rights. Hence, the notion of human rights derived from the teachings and values of Mahatma Phule is relevant to the present time and has been actualized.

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